

ANALYSIS OF AVAILABLE INNOVATIVE METHODS OF MEASURING AND CONTROLLING THE QUALITY OF ENERGY SUPPLY IN DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES

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Abstract: We reviewed modern power quality monitoring systems, smart grid technologies, distributed energy resources, preventive maintenance methods, active power filters, and energy management systems. Innovative approaches are found to be based on advances in transducers, measurements, data analysis, control algorithms and communication systems. They provide optimal power quality and reliable measurement results while improving the reliability, efficiency and stability of digital technology assets.

Keywords: modern energy quality monitoring systems, smart grid technologies, distributed energy resources, technical state prediction methods, active power filters, energy management systems, sensitivity, accuracy, measurement results, converters, control algorithms, reliability, efficiency, stability.

Аннотация: Нами рассмотрены современные системы мониторинга качества электроэнергии, технологии интеллектуальных сетей, распределенные энергетические ресурсы, методы профилактического обслуживания, фильтры активной мощности и системы управления энергопотреблением. Установлены, что инновационные подходы основаны на достижениях в области преобразователей, результатов измерений, анализа данных, алгоритмов управления и систем связи. Они обеспечивают оптимальное качество электропитания и надежные результаты измерений, одновременно повышая надежность, эффективность и стабильность объектов цифровых технологий.

Ключевые слова: современные системы мониторинга качества электроэнергии, технологии интеллектуальных сетей, распределенные энергоресурсы, методы прогнозирования технического состояния, фильтры активной мощности, системы энергоменеджмента, чувствительность, точность, результаты измерений, преобразователи, алгоритмы управления, надежность, эффективность, стабильность.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada energiya sifatini monitoring qilishning zamonaviy tizimlari, aqlli tarmoq texnologiyalari, taqsimlangan energiya resurslari, texnik holatni bashoratlash usullari, faol quvvat filtrlari va energiyani boshqarish tizimlarini muhokama qilamiz. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki mazkur innovatsion yondashuvlar energiya ta'minotining optimal sifatini ta'minlash uchun sezgirligi va aniqligi yuqori, hamda o'lchash natjalari ishonchli bo'lgan o'zgartkichlar, o'lchash natijalari va o'rganilgan ma'lumotlar tahlili, boshqaruv algoritmlari va aloqa tizimlaridagi yutuqlardan foydalanadi va shu bilan birga raqamli texnologiyalar ob'ektlarining ishonchliligi, samaradorligi va barqarorligini oshiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: energiya sifatini monitoring qilishning zamonaviy tizimlari, aqlli tarmoq texnologiyalari, taqsimlangan energiya resurslari, texnik holatni bashoratlash usullari, faol quvvat filtrlari, energiyani boshqarish tizimlari, sezgirlik, aniqlik, o'lchash natjalari, o'zgartkichlar, boshqaruv algoritmlari, ishonchlilik, samaradorlik, barqarorlik.

Digital technology facilities, such as data processing centres, telecommunications networks, and industrial automation systems, require a stable and high-quality power supply to ensure continuous operation and optimal energy consumption. However, traditional methods of power quality measurement and control may not be effective for the complex and dynamic characteristics of modern digital systems. Therefore, to effectively monitor and mitigate power quality issues in digital technology facilities, innovative approaches are required.

The increasing use of digital technologies in recent years has led to a rise in electricity demand, causing the existing energy infrastructure to operate under heavy load. The importance of providing reliable and high-quality power supply in digital technology facilities has increased due to the growing demand and proliferation of sensitive electronic equipment. Power quality issues, such as voltage sags, harmonics, and transients, can compromise electronic systems, digital equipment, and various technologies, including data integrity.

Therefore, innovative solutions are needed to address these issues. Below are some innovative ways to solve these problems:

- **Advanced Power Quality Control Systems:** Advanced power quality control systems represent significant advances in power quality management. These systems use high precision transducers and measuring devices to continuously measure key parameters such as voltage, current, frequency and harmonics. By collecting a much higher level of data than traditional monitoring systems, advanced monitoring systems provide more detailed and accurate results about electrical system performance.

One of the main advantages of advanced power quality monitoring systems is their ability to analyze large amounts of data in real time. By applying sophisticated data analysis algorithms, these systems can detect changes, trends, and anomalies that may indicate power quality issues. This real-time analysis allows facility operators to respond quickly to disturbances, minimizing their impact on power supplies and electronic equipment.

In addition, advanced power quality monitoring systems often have remote monitoring and diagnostic capabilities, allowing facility operators to monitor the stable operation of the power system from anywhere with an Internet connection. This remote access allows for proactive maintenance and troubleshooting, reducing power outages and increasing overall system reliability.

- **Smart Grid Technologies:** Smart grid technologies represent a paradigm shift in the way electricity is generated, distributed and consumed. At its core, a smart grid is an intelligent, digitally powered power grid that uses advanced communication, control and monitoring technologies to optimize the flow of electricity in real time.

One of the key components of a smart grid is an advanced metering infrastructure, which consists of smart metering devices installed on customers' premises to measure and monitor electricity consumption. These smart meters provide accurate, near-real-time data on energy consumption, allowing utilities to better understand and manage demand patterns.

In addition to advanced metering infrastructure, smart grids include modern switches, communication networks, and control systems throughout the power grid. These components allow utilities to identify and respond to power quality issues more quickly and efficiently. For example, switches built into power grids can detect voltage dips or surges, allowing utilities to disconnect and redirect power to minimize power outages.

Another key feature of smart grids is their ability to integrate distributed energy resources such as solar panels, wind turbines, and battery storage systems. By harnessing the power of

distributed energy resources, smart grids can increase grid stability and resilience to power outages and reduce dependence on centralized power generation.

- **Distributed Energy Resources:** Distributed energy resources are a diverse set of small-scale energy generation and storage technologies located close to the point of consumption. Distributed energy resources include solar photovoltaic module systems, wind turbines, thermal and hydroelectric power plants, and energy storage systems.

One of the main advantages of distributed energy resources is the ability to increase the reliability and resilience of the power grid. Distributed energy resources through local power generation can reduce dependence on centralized generation and transmission infrastructure, thereby reducing the risk of large-scale power outages.

Distributed energy resources also play a crucial role in improving the quality of energy in digital technology facilities. For example, solar photovoltaic module systems help mitigate voltage fluctuations by injecting power into the grid during periods of high demand. Similarly, energy storage systems can provide backup power during outages or supply power during periods of peak demand, helping to stabilize the grid and ensure power quality.

In addition to the direct impact on power quality, distributed energy resources also offer significant benefits, such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving energy efficiency, and providing opportunities for energy cost savings. As a result, deployment of distributed energy resources is expected to continue to grow in the coming years due to technological advancements, cost reductions, and supportive policies from developed countries.

- **Predictive Techniques:** Predictive techniques use data analysis and estimation algorithms to predict equipment failures before they occur. By analyzing historical data about equipment performance and power quality, predictive maintenance systems can detect changes or anomalies that may indicate impending failure.

One of the main benefits of predictive maintenance techniques is that they can reduce energy downtime and maintenance costs by allowing operators to address problems before they become outright failures. For example, if the predictive maintenance system detects a gradual increase in harmonic distortion in the power distribution system, this may indicate that the capacitor is starting to fail. By proactively replacing the capacitor, operators can avoid the power outages and high costs associated with a catastrophic failure.

Condition prediction techniques can be applied to a wide range of equipment in digital technology facilities, including transformers, automatic relays, UPS systems, and power distribution panels. By continuously monitoring equipment performance and power quality, predictive maintenance systems can provide facility operators with actionable guidance to optimize maintenance schedules, extend equipment life, and improve overall system reliability and stability.

- **Active Power Filters:** Active power filters are high-tech electronic devices used to solve power quality problems such as harmonics, voltage drops, and spikes. Unlike passive filters, which rely on passive components such as inductors and capacitors to filter harmonic currents, active power filters use active components such as power transistors and control algorithms to actively introduce corrective currents into the electrical system.

One of the main advantages of active power filters is their ability to provide dynamic and flexible compensation for power quality problems. By continuously monitoring the voltage and current waveforms, active power filters can quickly detect disturbances such as harmonic oscillations or voltage fluctuations and generate compensating currents to cancel them out.

Active power filters are particularly well suited to environments with non-linear loads such as data centers and industrial facilities where harmonic oscillations are a common problem. By filtering out harmonics and other power quality disturbances, active power filters can improve the efficiency and reliability of electrical systems, reduce equipment downtime, and extend equipment life.

In addition to the main function of power quality correction, active power filters can also provide additional capabilities such as power factor correction and voltage stabilization. By providing a balanced and stable power supply, active power filters help ensure the reliable operation of highly sensitive electronic equipment and reduce the risk of equipment damage or data loss.

- **Energy Management Systems:** Energy management systems are software-based platforms used to monitor, control and optimize energy consumption in digital technology facilities. Energy management systems platforms integrate data from a wide range of sources, including power quality monitors, energy meters, building management systems and weather forecasts, to provide facility operators with real-time information on energy consumption and demand changes. allows lateral vision.

One of the key features of energy management systems platforms is their ability to perform real-time energy monitoring and analysis. By continuously collecting and analyzing energy usage data, energy management systems platforms can identify energy savings opportunities, identify anomalies or inefficiencies, and provide actionable guidance to facility operators.

Another key feature of energy management systems platforms is their ability to optimize energy consumption using predictive methods. Using historical data and predictive analytics algorithms, energy management systems platforms can predict future energy demand, identify potential energy savings opportunities, and optimize energy use accordingly.

Conclusion: To ensure optimal performance, reliability, and stability, it is essential to measure and control the quality of power supply in digital technology facilities. Promising solutions for solving complex problems related to power quality in the modern digital environment include intelligent energy quality monitoring systems, smart grid technologies, distributed energy resources, technical condition prediction methods, active power filters, and energy management systems. By employing innovative approaches, digital technology facilities can enhance the resilience, efficiency, and environmental sustainability of energy supply systems in the future. Ongoing scientific research in this field is crucial for the development of modern technologies and to meet the evolving needs of the digital economy.

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